

Is Science Truly Objective?

According to the Oxford definition, the 'ontological objective reality' is what is left when we remove all possible observers (reality) and its content is independent from anybody who could potentially peek at it (objectivity). The barebone existence...

However, this very logical, coherent definition is so good that it makes it basically unusable for any practical tasks. Especially for science. This definition is like a black hole with its event horizon - peeking inside it strictly forbidden. And this is a major problem for a scientist, who - according to the scientific method - must look at the object, measure it, break it. Without doing so - no data, no hypothesis, no theory. No science.

In practice it means that by applying the method, scientists are bound to generate friction with objectivity... We will have a closer look at that friction.

First, it happens, at least, on two planes. One - the scale of objects being investigated. Second - the scientist's own cognitive, epistemological (and phenomenological) apparatus.

Let's look at the scales. Observation necessarily involves physical interaction with the observed object. At quantum scales the resulting decoherence changes the object of observation irreversibly. A scientist is not simply 'observing' reality - they are actively reshaping it. Now, 'objectivity' takes a weird angle... how to describe objectively an object which morphs when you just simply look at it?

If we take the other extreme - the cosmic scale - we move into the realm of the Einstein's Theories of Relativity. One of the most famous consequences of their relativistic effects is the "'twins' paradox". Here, one could say that the experiment actually changes the scientist themselves. Again, how do we interpret this phenomenon in terms of 'scientific objectivity' when the description of events depends on the choice of the space-time reference frame...?

Of course, then we have the middle scale, the one we are most familiar with (where the Newton mechanics operates). Here, in general, the size of objects investigated is comparable to the size of the investigator. And this range behaves "decently" - objective predictions do not typically produce paradoxes.

The second plane - our human cognitive apparatus. No one, scientists included, is 'absolutely objective' (whatever it might mean). We are all biased - in different ways. But how this could affect the results of application of the scientific method? Well, one possible way is via language we use. I, personally, feel comfortable in two languages and I clearly see that I switch between them automatically to better express different concepts, depending on their content. Extrapolating my subjective observation, maybe it is not accidental that English is the universal language of science. Not only because it promotes a relatively analytic and standardized mode of scientific communication but also because it offers the particular cognition frame for its users. Meaning - maybe some concepts are more naturally expressed than others because of the very structure of the language? How would our scientific worldview look like if the universal frame would be, say, Mandarin?

These are, of course, not identical problems, but they may share a structural feature: it could be impossible to interrogate reality independently from the framework through which it is

interrogated. In both planes it seems to matter what kind of lens you use to look at your research object, both physically and mentally (see: <https://philpapers.org/rec/MARWHW-3>)

At this stage, I am not attempting to answer my own question. I leave it to you. But the conundrum of 'truly objective science' may actually lie beyond our (current) 'epistemic capability cone' (see <https://philpapers.org/rec/MARWAE-9>)...

Acknowledgments

The author acknowledges the assistance of AI Claude (Anthropic), ChatGPT (OpenAI) and Google AI systems in improving the manuscript.